

1 **Application of Post-Violet IR Single Aliquot Regenerative Dose (pVIR-SAR) Protocol**
2 **for Natural Polymineral Fine and Coarse Grain Samples**

3 Monika Devi^{a,b,c*}, Malika Singhal^{a,b}, Parth Khanduri^d, Naveen Chauhan^a, Ashok Kumar
4 Singhvi^{a,e}

5 ^a*AMOPH division, Physical Research Laboratory, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad-380009, India*

6 ^b*Indian Institute of Technology, Gandhinagar-382355, India.*

7 ^c*Institute for Interdisciplinary Experimental Research in Bio-Nano-Science, Babes-Bolyai*
8 *University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania.*

9 ^d*Department of Physical Science, P. D. Patel Institute of Applied Sciences, Charotar*
10 *University of Science and Technology, CHARUSAT, Changa 388421, Gujarat, India.*

11 ^e*Institute of Marine Sciences, Shantou University, Shantou, 515063 China.*

12 *email: monikaparmar678@gmail.com

13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Devi et al. (2024) characterised a post Violet Infrared Stimulated Luminescence (pVIRSL)
15 signal and developed a post Violet Infrared Single Aliquot Regenerative dose (pVIR-SAR)
16 protocol for estimation of paleodoses. The protocol provides an opportunity for measuring
17 polymineral samples as violet stimulation prior to IRSL measurement, bleaches natural
18 luminescence signal of quartz and makes it possible to probe photo-transferred charges in
19 feldspar through IR stimulation. This study presents the results of pVIR-SAR protocol on
20 natural polymineral fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (90-150 μm) grain samples, including volcanic
21 ash, pottery and fluvial deposits from varied geological provenances.

22 The results show that pVIR-SAR ages of both polymineral fine and coarse grain samples are
23 consistent with geological reasoning and available age controls thereby suggests that with the
24 use of pVIR-SAR protocol, mineral separation can be dispensed. This study also reports on
25 the bleachability, athermal fading rates and alpha efficiencies of pVIRSL for these samples
26 and corresponding results are compared with IRSL at 50 °C and post IR IRSL (pIRIR) at 290
27 °C. The pVIRSL signal has a better bleachability and reproducibility compared to pIRIRSL
28 signal. For the fluvial deposits dated in this study, the fine-grain samples provide ages
29 consistent with the expected chronology.

30 **KEYWORDS:** Post violet infrared stimulated luminescence; pIRIRSL; athermal fading;
31 polymineral samples; K-feldspar; Na-feldspar; fine-grains; coarse-grains.

32 **INTRODUCTION**

33 Varied luminescence signals from quartz and feldspar are used for luminescence dating.
34 These signals are obtained through multiple combinations of optical and thermal stimulations.
35 Natural sediments are a mixture of minerals and applications of luminescence dating to rock
36 slices and fine grains (4–11 µm) require the tedium of physical, chemical and optical
37 isolation of luminescence signals from specific mineral phases. This is challenging when the
38 sample amount is small or the grain sizes are small to permit ease of mineral separation.

39 For coarse grains, dating protocols rely on the separation of a single mineral type such that
40 luminescence from other minerals is either eliminated through chemical procedures and/or
41 minimized through measurement protocols with mineral specific stimulation sequences and
42 optical windows for luminescence detection. Blue/Green light stimulated luminescence
43 (BLSL/GLSL) from feldspar grains and from inclusions contaminate BLSL of quartz.
44 Therefore, efforts are needed to separate pure quartz and if needed, minimize feldspar
45 contamination to BLSL of quartz through the use of appropriate optical windows (Banerjee et

46 al., 2001; Jain and Singhvi, 2001; Wallinga et al., 2002) or through time resolved
47 luminescence measurements (Denby et al., 2006; Thomsen et al., 2008a; Ankjærsgaard et al.,
48 2010). Infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) prebleach to isolate quartz BLSL/GLSL is
49 also used (Jain and Singhvi, 2001; Robert, 2003, 2007; Qin et al., 2021).

50 Contrastingly, the presence of traces of quartz in feldspar separates is ignored, as IRSL
51 measured at low temperatures only arises from feldspars (Hütt et al., 1988) and the
52 luminescence sensitivity of quartz is significantly lower than feldspars. Optical dating using
53 feldspar grains include IRSL (Wallinga et al., 2000) and its variants such as post IR IRSL
54 (pIRIRSL; Buylaert et al., 2009, 2011, 2012), multiple elevated temperature pIRIR (MET-
55 pIRIR; Li and Li, 2011), post violet IR stimulated luminescence (pVIRSL; Devi et al., 2022),
56 re-distributed IRSL (Morthekai et al., 2015) and IR photoluminescence (IRPL) (Prasad et al.,
57 2017; Kumar et al., 2021). Earlier studies on samples of mixed mineralogy and without any
58 sample separation indicated deviations of estimated ages from expected ages, which is
59 attributed to mixed signals, variable grain sizes, and lack of standardized protocols (Kook et
60 al., 2011; Stone et al., 2015; Munyikwa et al., 2021).

61 Besides coarse grains (>90 μm), fine grains (4 -11 μm) of mixed mineralogy are also used for
62 estimating ages. Zimmerman (1971) developed the use of fine polymineral grains for
63 luminescence dating of fired pottery and provided an understanding of alpha efficiency,
64 aspects of which were later refined by Bowman and Huntley, (1984) and Singhvi and Aitken,
65 (1978). Procedures to separate fine grains quartz using silica-saturated hydrofluorosilicic acid
66 has been developed (Berger et al., 1980; Mejdahl and Christiansen, 1994) but its routine use
67 has not been seen due to long duration of cumbersome chemical processing.

68 Devi et al. (2022) reported the pVIRSL signal from feldspar. This is an IRSL signal after a
69 violet stimulation of K-feldspar, and has a near-zero athermal fading. A single aliquot

70 regeneration dose protocol using pVIRSL (pVIR-SAR) was developed which provided ages
71 consistent with available controls (Devi et al., 2024)). Violet stimulation bleaches the
72 luminescence of quartz and simultaneously photo-transfers charges from deep traps to IR
73 traps feldspar, which are then probed using IR stimulation. This suggests selective detection
74 of the feldspar luminescence in polymineral samples without contamination by luminescence
75 from other minerals. The present study tests this hypothesis and measures equivalent dose
76 results using the pVIR-SAR protocol on mixed mineralogy (polymineral) fine and coarse
77 grain samples. The work compares the obtained results with BLSL dating of quartz (Murray
78 and Wintle, 2000), IRSL at 50 °C (Wallinga et al., 2000) and pIRIRSL at 290 °C from
79 feldspar (Buylaert et al., 2009). Further, data on the bleachability of pVIRSL under daylight
80 exposure, its athermal fading rates and alpha efficiencies are reported and compared with
81 IRSL and pIRIRSL signals.

82 **SAMPLES AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP**

83 Table 1 details thirteen samples with independently estimated depositional ages used in the
84 study. These samples are from diverse locations and depositional histories and include
85 samples from three volcanic ash deposits, four pottery artefacts, and six fluvial sediments,
86 with luminescence ages in the range of 500 yr – 68 ka (Table 1). PRL23-01, -02 and -03 are
87 volcanic ash samples and of these PRL23-03 has age controls from ages of sediments above
88 and below the ash layer (Anil et al., 2025). PRL23-04 and -05 are pottery samples from
89 southern India. PRL23-06 and -07 are hollow Iron Age urns and the X-ray diffraction data for
90 these two samples show the presence of sanidine (Morthekai, P., Personal communication,
91 2023). PRL23-08 and -09 are fluvial samples from Tamil Nadu with BLSL ages as controls
92 and for these, both fine grain and coarse grain are analysed. PRL23-10 and -11 are fine grain
93 fluvial samples from a single stratigraphic unit (Prasad, R.K., Personal communication,

94 2023). Samples MHK-09-12 and -13 are fluvial sediments from Mehtakheri, with age
95 controls based on BLSL of quartz (Mishra et al., 2013).

96 The volcanic ash and pottery artefacts are fine-grained and therefore are suitable only for
97 polymineral fine-grain measurements. The sediment samples are collected using specially
98 designed sampling steel tubes (Chandel et al., 2006) and opened under subdued red light ($\lambda >$
99 630 nm). The top and bottom ~3 cm portion of sample in the pipe is used for radioactivity
100 and moisture content measurements. Sediment in the interior of the tube is used for
101 luminescence measurements. For pottery samples, the outer few mm of daylight-exposed
102 surface is removed and this fraction and the nearby sediments are used for dose rate
103 measurements. The interior is used for the equivalent dose estimation. All coarse and fine
104 grain samples are treated with 1N HCl and 30% H₂O₂ to remove the carbonates and organic
105 matter, respectively. Fine grain samples are then treated with 0.01N sodium oxalate solution
106 for deflocculation. The desired grain size of 4 to 11 μm is obtained using Stokes Law
107 (Zimmerman, 1971). Equal volumes of grains in suspension are pipetted on to aluminium
108 discs in vials and dried at 45 °C. The coarse grain fractions are obtained by dry sieving,
109 etching with 10% hydrofluoric (HF) acid for 40 min (to remove alpha skin; Fleming, 1966,
110 1970, Goedicke, 1984), followed by 30 min treatment with 12N HCl to convert insoluble
111 fluorides into soluble chlorides and then washed with distilled water.

112 Luminescence measurements are carried out in the Risø-TL/OSL DA-20 reader (Bøtter-
113 Jensen et al., 2010; Lapp et al., 2015) at the Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad,
114 during the year 2023–2024. The stimulations use IR (850 \pm 33 nm) LEDs, and a violet laser
115 diode (405 \pm 15 nm). Detection windows comprise filters permitting transmission in the 327–
116 353 nm region [U-340 + Brightline 340/26] for violet stimulation, and in 320–520 nm region
117 [BG-39 + BG-3 (blue)] for IR stimulation. These are coupled to an ET 9107B photomultiplier

118 tube with a quartz window (Devi et al., 2022; 2024). An indigenous daylight simulator
119 comprising Osram ultra-vitalux 300 W sunlamp filtered through a glass window is used as a
120 surrogate for daylight bleaching of the samples.

121 **METHODOLOGY**

122 *pVIRSL signal of mixed mineralogy samples*

123 The characteristics of pVIRSL signal of pure feldspar samples has been discussed by Devi et.
124 al. (2024). In this study, the suitability of the pVIR-SAR protocol and the assumption that in
125 an ensemble of mixed mineralogy (e.g. quartz, feldspar and others) pVIRSL signal results
126 only from the feldspars is investigated. The pVIRSL at 200 °C of Na-feldspar (NaF), K-
127 feldspar (KF), and Risø calibration quartz (batch 122) is measured after a cut-heat to 500 °C
128 (to remove any signal from the previous dose), followed by a 20 Gy dose, a preheat at 250 °C
129 for 60 s, and violet stimulation at 50 °C for 100 s. The weight normalised pVIRSL signals are
130 shown in Figure 1. The pVIRSL from an empty stainless-steel disc is also included to show
131 the background signal.

132 *Equivalent dose measurements*

133 The pVIR-SAR protocol (Devi et al., 2024); Supplementary Table 1) is used for equivalent
134 dose (D_e) measurements. In pVIR-SAR protocol, IRSL at 200 °C for 100 s is measured after
135 violet stimulation at 50 °C for 100 s and a preheat at 250 °C for 60 s. A test dose of 50–80%
136 of the expected dose is then applied. At the end of the each SAR cycle, VSL and IRSL
137 exposures at 350 °C for 200 s are used to remove charges from deeper traps. Typically, 15 to
138 24 aliquots are measured per sample. As the over-dispersion in equivalent doses is less than
139 30% therefore the central age model (CAM) is applied. D_e values of the aliquots having
140 recuperation $\leq 5\%$ of the natural signal, a recycling ratio within 10% of unity and signal to
141 noise (S/N) ratio > 3 are accepted for dose computation. The pVIR-SAR ages are compared

142 with BLSL-SAR ages for quartz mineral separates, IR-SAR ages for (Supplementary Table
143 2) for young samples, and the pIRIR-SAR (Supplementary Table 3) protocol for older
144 samples. For pottery samples with the presence of Sanidine, pIRIR-SAR ages are used.
145 Laboratory residual doses are not subtracted from the equivalent dose values. As reported in
146 the previous literature that natural residual doses are much smaller than from the residual
147 doses estimated in the laboratory (Sobhati et al., 2012; Buylaert et al., 2012; Li et al., 2014;
148 Avram et al., 2022).

149 *Fading rate measurements*

150 The athermal fading rates (g-values) for all signal are estimated using Auclair et al. (2003)
151 and Devi et al. (2022). The delay times is based on the equivalent dose of the samples and
152 ranged from one to ~ten days. The t_c (time since irradiation for the prompt measurement)
153 values are normalised to a fixed value of 2 days (Huntley and Lamothe, 2001; Auclair et al.,
154 2003). Athermal fading rates of pVIRSL for polymineral samples are computed by plotting
155 test dose normalised pVIRSL intensities against delay time (Supplementary Figure 1, 2 and
156 3). The fading corrections for ages are carried out using the method suggested by Huntley and
157 Lamothe (2001), with all error propagations considered. The fading rates are measured for all
158 the samples (Supplementary Figures 1 to 3), along with one museum sodium feldspar (Figure
159 2).

160 *Laboratory residual dose and dose recovery tests*

161 The laboratory residual doses for are estimated after the five-hour exposure under a filtered
162 sun-lamp. For the dose recovery tests, a known dose approximately equal to the expected
163 dose is administered after a 5h sunlamp bleach, and subsequently recovered using the pVIR-
164 SAR and pIRIR-SAR protocols. An average of recovered doses of six aliquots per sample is
165 used for dose recovery ratio calculation. The laboratory residual doses are subtracted from the

166 recovered doses. Table 2 and Table 3 presents the residual doses and dose recovery ratios for
167 pVIR-SAR and pIRIR-SAR protocols, respectively.

168 *Alpha efficiency and dose rate measurements*

169 Alpha efficiencies (a-values) for IRSL, pIRIRSL and pVIRSL signals are measured. The
170 samples are bleached under the sun-lamp for five hours followed by irradiation of six aliquots
171 of each sample under vacuum using a calibrated ^{241}Am alpha source (Singhvi and Aitken,
172 1978) for 120 mins. Then, equivalent beta doses for the alpha dosed aliquots are estimated
173 and alpha efficiencies are computed following Aitken, (1985; pp. 308-317).

174 Elemental concentration of radioactive nuclides is measured using a high purity Germanium
175 (HPGe) detector. The dose rates are calculated using a Dose Rate calculator (DRc) software
176 under an infinite matrix assumption (Tsokolas et al., 2016). Wherever required, volumetric
177 corrections are applied to meet the infinite dose matrix criterion (Appendix I). The
178 conversion factors used in DRc software followed Guérin et al. (2011). The dose rate
179 computation assumed internal potassium (^{40}K) of $12.5 \pm 0.5\%$ (Huntley and Baril, 1997) and
180 Rubidium (^{87}Rb) at 400 ± 100 ppm (Huntley and Hancock, 2001). The cosmic ray
181 contribution to dose rate is estimated using Prescott and Hutton (1994).

182 **RESULTS**

183 *Purity of pVIRSL signal to feldspar from mixed mineralogy*

184 Figure 1 compares the weight-normalised pVIRSL decay curves for quartz, NaF, and KF and
185 empty stainless-steel discs. The pVIRSL from both quartz and the empty disc are at
186 background levels and KF and NaF had the pVIRSL signal about 10^2 times the background.
187 This suggested that in polymineral samples, feldspar is the key source of pVIRSL. With this
188 premise, pVIRSL of both the fine and coarse grain polymineral samples was explored.

189 *Equivalent dose estimation*

190 Supplementary Figures 1 to 3 provide typical pVIRSL optical decay and dose-response
191 curves (DRCs) for the samples. All samples displayed sufficient signal (S/N ratio > 3). The
192 DRCs are fitted with a single saturating exponential function. The recuperation of all samples
193 is less than 5% of the natural signal, and the recycling ratios are within 10% of unity. Table 2
194 and 3 provides fading corrected pVIR-SAR equivalent doses along with IR-, and pIRIR-SAR
195 based estimates. With the exception of coarse grain PRL23-08 and -09, the pVIRSL
196 equivalent doses are consistent with the expected doses. For PRL23-08 coarse grains, the
197 pVIR-SAR equivalent dose is 236 ± 6 Gy, the corresponding pIRIR-SAR dose is 345 ± 23
198 Gy. For PRL23-09, these are 315 ± 16 Gy and 422 ± 22 Gy, respectively. However,
199 corresponding coarse grain quartz equivalent doses, converted to feldspar equivalent doses of
200 are 110 ± 6 Gy (Quartz dose = 94 ± 4 Gy) and 149 ± 9 Gy (Quartz dose = 126 ± 6 Gy),
201 respectively. A threefold dose overestimation is obtained using the pIRIR-SAR protocol and
202 twofold using the pVIR-SAR protocol. The fine grain pVIR-SAR equivalent doses for the
203 same samples are 151 ± 2 Gy and 219 ± 5 Gy and are closer to the expected equivalent doses
204 (Table 3).

205 *Athermal fading*

206 Figure 2 shows the variation of test dose normalised intensity with delay time for sodium
207 feldspar (NaF) sample. The weighted mean of athermal fading rates of fifteen aliquots of NaF
208 is $0.1 \pm 0.2\%$ per decade. Supplementary Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 presents the normalised
209 intensity with delay time for pVIRSL for all fine grain samples. For six out of the eleven fine
210 grain samples, pVIRSL athermal fading rates are $g \leq 1.1\%$ per decade (Table 2, Figure 3). No
211 age corrections are carried out for these samples, as low fading rates would not change the
212 age estimations to any appreciable extent (Buylaert et al., 2012). The g-values for pVIRSL
213 for remaining five fine grain samples PRL23-02, -05, -06, -07 and -10 are 2.3 ± 0.2 , $1.4 \pm$

214 0.1, 5.9 ± 0.6 , 4.0 ± 0.4 and $1.3 \pm 0.4\%$ per decade, respectively. For IRSL and pIRIRSL
215 signals, only PRL23-09 fluvial fine grain sample have g-value of $\leq 1.1\%$ per decade (Table 3,
216 Figure 3). Other fine grain samples have athermal fading rates $>1.1\%$ per decade.

217 For polymineralic coarse grains, three out of four samples yield fading rates $\leq 1\%$ per decade
218 for pVIRSL (Table 2). In contrast, the pIRIRSL g-values are consistently $\geq 1\%$ per decade for
219 all four samples.

220 *Laboratory residual dose and dose recovery test*

221 The pVIR-SAR laboratory residual doses are ranged from 3.3 ± 0.2 Gy to 10.0 ± 0.2 Gy and
222 for pIRIR-SAR range from 10.3 ± 0.6 Gy to 34.4 ± 0.5 Gy (Table 2 and 3). The laboratory
223 residual doses of pVIR-SAR are 30 to 70% lower than the pIRIR-SAR and accord with Devi
224 et al. (2024). Thus, pVIRSL is bleached by daylight more efficiently compared to pIRIRSL.
225 Residual doses of the pottery samples are not measured, as firing at temperatures above 400
226 °C should have erased all residual signals. The dose recovery ratios for pVIR-SAR range
227 from 0.94 to 1.06, whereas those for pIRIR-SAR range from 0.93 to 1.12 (Tables 2 and 3).

228 *Dose rate determination*

229 *Alpha efficiency*

230 Table 4 and Figure 4 provide alpha efficiencies for pVIRSL, IRSL, and pIRIRSL signals.
231 Alpha efficiencies of pVIRSL for volcanic ash samples viz., PRL23-01, -02 and -03 are 0.067
232 ± 0.004 , 0.088 ± 0.004 , and 0.060 ± 0.002 and their pIRIRSL a-values are 0.086 ± 0.007 ,
233 0.119 ± 0.006 and 0.083 ± 0.004 , indicating that a-values for pVIRSL are lower than
234 pIRIRSL. For all fluvial samples, a-values follows the order: IRSL $<$ pVIRSL $<$ pIRIRSL. In
235 contrast, the order of a-values are reversed for pottery samples i.e., IRSL $>$ pVIRSL $>$
236 pIRIRSL. Further, a correlation between alpha efficiencies and fading values is explored
237 following the suggestion from Singhvi, (1981). As seen in Figure 5, the g-values are constant

238 with changing a-values except for pottery samples PRL23-06 and 07, where fading rates are
239 high.

240 *Annual Dose Rate*

241 Table 4 provides the data on concentration of radioactive nuclides, water contents and depth
242 of the samples from surface. For the dose rate computation for polymineral sample, a uniform
243 internal dose rate is considered with the assumption that only feldspar grains provide
244 pVIRSL. Sohbaty et al. (2013) reported that in cases, when the range of beta particle exceeds
245 the grain size used (90-150 μm), and if the ^{40}K concentration is uniformly distributed in a
246 grain, the dependence of internal beta dose for potassium concentration $< 5\%$ and is
247 insignificant. The dose rate contribution for fine grains due to internal ^{40}K is $< 1\%$ of the total
248 dose rate thus provide minimal contribution to the total dose rate. Therefore, uniform values
249 of internal potassium and rubidium are considered for the dose rate calculations of all
250 polymineral samples. For PRL23-03 volcanic ash sample, considering the volumetric
251 corrections (Appendix I) the total dose rate is reduced by 0.7 Gy/ka (Table 2). Pottery
252 samples PRL23-06 and 23-07 were hollow urns and therefore, the gamma doses are
253 computed with geometric corrections using the dose rate from pottery and ambient soils
254 (Morthekai, P., Personal communication, 2023).

255 *Ages*

256 *Fine grains*

257 Fine grains measurements are carried out on volcanic ash, pottery and fluvial samples. Table
258 2 provides the results for pVIR ages and Table 3 provides IR and pIRIR ages. Ages discussed
259 below are corrected for fading wherever applicable.

260 *Volcanic ash*

261 The pVIR ages of volcanic ash samples PRL23-01, -02, and -03 are 17 ± 1 ka, 26 ± 1 ka and
262 28 ± 3 ka, respectively (Table 2, Figure 6). These are consistent with the pIRIR ages of $17 \pm$
263 1 ka, 21 ± 1 ka, and 32 ± 3 ka (Table 3). For PRL23-03, pVIR ages are consistent with
264 sediments above and below the volcanic ash layer, with pIRIR ages of 29 ± 1 and 34 ± 2 ka
265 for, respectively (Anil et al., 2025).

266 *Pottery samples*

267 The pVIR ages of pottery samples PRL23-04, -05, -06, and -07 are plotted in Figure 6 and
268 shown in Table 2. For PRL23-04, pVIR age is 1.8 times the IR age. The pVIR age of PRL23-
269 05 is consistent with IR age within 20% offset. For PRL23-06 and PRL23-07, IRSL at 50 °C
270 yielded fading rates $>10\%$ per decade which cannot be corrected using the fading correction
271 age models (Huntley and Lamothe, 2001). Therefore, pIRIR ages are considered as
272 independent ages. The pVIR ages of PRL23-06 and PRL23-07 are 3.3 ± 0.4 ka and 3.3 ± 0.2
273 ka, and the pIRIR ages are 3.4 ± 0.3 ka and 4.1 ± 0.4 ka, respectively. Fluvial fine grains
274 samples, PRL23-10 and PRL23-11 returned pVIR age of 2.0 ± 0.1 ka and 2.8 ± 0.1 ka,
275 respectively. The pVIR age of PRL23-10 is approximately twice the IR age, while the pVIR
276 age of PRL23-11 agrees with the IR age within 20% offset.

277 *Coarse grains: Fluvial samples*

278 The pVIR and pIRIR ages of four polymineral coarse grain fluvial samples are measured, of
279 which MHK-09-12, -13 are consistent with quartz BLSL ages (Mishra et al., 2013) (Table 2
280 and 3). The pVIR and pIRIR ages of PRL23-08 are 66 ± 4 ka and 96 ± 8 ka and for PRL23-
281 09 are 117 ± 10 ka and 156 ± 14 ka, respectively. The pVIR ages are twice and the pIRIR
282 ages are thrice the quartz BLSL ages (Table 2 and 3; Figure 7). Fuller et al. (1994) suggested
283 that in fluvial contexts fine grains might be better bleached as compared to coarse grains due
284 to the mode of their transport. Therefore, for PRL23-08 and 09 samples, the ages of fine grain

285 fractions are estimated. The pVIR fine-grain ages of these samples are 39 ± 1 ka and 73 ± 3
286 ka and are consistent with quartz BLSL ages of 31 ± 2 ka and 59 ± 3 ka within 20% offset.
287 However, the pIRIR fine grain ages for these samples are still twice the expected ages (Figure
288 7).

289 **DISCUSSION**

290 This study reports the use of pVIRSL for polymineral fine and coarse grain samples for
291 dating without mineral separation. Violet stimulation removes signals from minerals such as
292 quartz, and from the principal trap of feldspar (Figure 1). At the same time, it photo-transfers
293 some charges from deep traps to the principal trap of feldspars. These are then probed
294 through IR stimulation. The pVIRSL signal is a photo-transferred signal originating from the
295 deep traps of feldspars or in some cases, charges from the principal traps also participate
296 (Devi et al., 2024). Therefore, in polymineralic samples, the pVIRSL signal primarily arises
297 from feldspars (Figure 1). In feldspars, the IRSL emission of sodium rich feldspar peaks in
298 the yellow-green emission band and the K-feldspar emission peaks in the violet region of the
299 spectral emission (Krbetschek et al., 1997; Baril and Huntley, 2003). Sohbati et al., 2013
300 suggested that the pIRIR signal of sodium-rich feldspar, in a blue window is due to
301 potassium-rich feldspar as both sodium and potassium feldspar co-exist in an exsolution
302 form. However, the significant signal observed in Na-feldspar (NaF) in our study in the blue
303 window indicates that it also emits in this region (Figure 1). Thomsen et al. (2008b) reported
304 higher athermal fading in Na-feldspar than K-feldspar. The near zero fading in NaF sample
305 suggest that pVIRSL probes charges from the stable traps in Na-feldspar, further supporting
306 the athermal stability of pVIRSL in feldspars (Devi et al., 2024). Furthermore, lower fading
307 rates for pVIRSL compared to IRSL and pIRIRSL in majority of the samples indicates that it
308 probes charges from more stable trapped charge centres. The higher pVIRSL fading rates for
309 PRL23-06 and PRL23-07 compared to pIRIRSL could possibly be due to the presence of

310 sanidine (Morthekai, P., Personal communication, 2023) as suggested by Polymeris et al.
311 (2022) that sanidine IRSL exhibits higher fading among the three groups of K-feldspar.

312 A general agreement of pVIR ages for all volcanic, pottery and fluvial fine grains with other
313 signals suggest usability of pVIRSL for polymineral samples (Figure 6). For polymineral
314 coarse grains from MHK-09-12 and MHK-09-13, both pVIRSL and pIRIRSL ages are
315 consistent with the quartz BLSL ages (Figure 7). Overestimation of pVIRSL and pIRIRSL
316 ages for PRL23-08 and PRL23-09 samples compared to quartz BLSL ages for the fluvial
317 samples indicates that feldspar grains were not bleached properly. However, lower
318 overestimation seen in pVIRSL ages compared to pIRIRSL suggests that pVIRSL is more
319 readily bleached (Table 2 and 3). For same set of samples, agreement of pVIR fine grain ages
320 with quartz BLSL ages indicates better bleachability of pVIRSL of fine grains and they have
321 seen a greater amount of daylight exposure compared to coarse grains, which is consistent
322 with Fuller et al. (1994). These results suggest that the pVIR-SAR protocol for fine grains is
323 effective in addressing the challenges of dating fluvial samples. Furthermore, the lower
324 laboratory residual doses for pVIR-SAR compared to pIRIR-SAR support the greater
325 bleachability of pVIRSL than pIRIRSL. The reason for more efficient bleaching of pVIRSL
326 compared to pIRIRSL needs further exploration. We consider that an important advantage of
327 pVIRSL of fine grains is for samples such as from Himalaya where quartz BLSL is not easily
328 measurable on account of its low sensitivity and coarse grain feldspars show inadequate
329 bleachability in respect of their IRSL.

330 In computing equivalent doses, we did not subtract laboratory residual doses from the
331 estimated doses as we consider that the SAR protocol subsumes in it the residual correction
332 and subtracting it again would lead to over correction. Further, the residual doses measured in
333 the laboratory after five hours of exposure under a filtered sun-lamp may not be actual
334 representative of residual dose as it will contain some part from the unbleached component

335 (Sobhati et al., 2012; Buylaert et al., 2012; Li et al., 2014). Different methods, such as
336 intensity subtraction and using the intercept from the linear correlation between dose and
337 laboratory residual doses, have been used to calculate residual dose in nature (Li et al., 2013;
338 Brezeanu et al., 2021; Avram et al., 2022). The residual doses estimated using these methods
339 were much lower than those obtained after five hours of exposure to the sun-lamp. It is also
340 supported by the fact that the doses estimated for the surface samples were close to zero (0.09
341 ± 0.14 Gy; Devi et al., 2024). Furthermore, in samples MHK-09-12 and MHK-09-13, quartz
342 and feldspar ages are concordant even without subtracting the laboratory residual dose,
343 further supporting that the residual doses estimated in the laboratory are higher than those in
344 nature. To provide an appreciation of the effect of subtraction of residual dose, we also
345 provide the doses and ages with laboratory residual dose subtraction for both the pVIR-SAR
346 and pIRIR-SAR protocols in supplementary Table 4. Based on these observations, we suggest
347 that surface samples from the dated site may serve as a reasonable approximation of the
348 natural residual dose. This aspect will be explored further. Variations in a -values between
349 samples and signals reflect differences in defect states. Higher a -values of pIRIRSL than
350 pVIRSL and IRSL suggest larger density of charge traps responsible for pIRIRSL. However,
351 a reverse trend in the pottery samples suggests that firing possibly reorganize density of
352 charge traps. This requires further study and exploration.

353 **CONCLUSIONS**

354 This study tested the potential of the pVIR-SAR protocol for natural polymineral fine grain
355 (4–11 μm) and coarse (90–150 μm) samples from various depositional environments and
356 compared pVIR-SAR ages with, BLSL-SAR ages from quartz, IR-SAR ($T = 50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and
357 pIRIR-SAR ($T = 290\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) ages from feldspar. pVIRSL showed lower fading than IRSL and
358 pIRIRSL, except in PRL23-06 and PRL23-07, likely due to the presence of sanidine. The
359 dependence of alpha efficiencies on different signals implies that caution is needed when

360 using constant or assumed alpha efficiencies. The pVIR-SAR protocol is a promising tool for
361 dating polymineral fine and coarse grain sediments. Its rapid bleaching, reproducibility, low
362 athermal fading rates, and absence of interference from quartz pVIRSL would permit direct
363 dating without mineral separation. The protocol worked well for volcanic ash, pottery fine
364 grains, and fluvial fine and coarse polymineral samples. It enabled dating of polymineral fine
365 and coarse grain sediments from a few years to ~68 ka, with ages consistent with geological
366 reasoning and existing controls. Compared to pIRIR-SAR, pVIR-SAR yields ages that agree
367 with quartz ages for fine grain fractions of fluvial samples used in the study. Overall, the
368 study suggest that pVIR-SAR could be a valuable tool for addressing the dating challenges
369 posed by fluvial samples and may serve as a reliable alternative dating method for precise age
370 determination.

371

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384

385 **CONTRIBUTIONS**

386 Monika Devi: Conceptualisation, methodology, writing (first draft), data curation, and
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388 Malika Singhal: Data curation and analysis

389 Parth Khanduri: Data curation

390 Naveen Chauhan: Conceptualisation, Supervision and writing (Editing and reviewing).

391 Ashok Kumar Singhvi: Conceptualisation, Supervision and writing (Editing and reviewing).

392 **APPENDIX I**

393 *Volumetric correction for heterogeneous sedimentary layers*

394 The PRL23-03 sample has an average thickness of around 30 cm for the ash layer. The
395 underlying and overlying sediment layers have lower radioactive concentrations compared to
396 the ash layer deposit. In this case, the infinite matrix assumption is not valid gamma radiation
397 for ash layer sample. Therefore, volume corrections for the gamma dose rate are made. The
398 ash layer is approximately 30 cm thick, as illustrated in supplementary Figure 5a. A sphere of
399 radius 'r' equal to 30 cm with three layers: two sedimentary (1 and 3) and an ash layer (2) is
400 considered (Supplementary Figure 5b). The volumetric corrections for the dose deposited by
401 gamma rays in the ash sample is given below:

402
$$Volume_s * \gamma_s = Volume_1 * \gamma_1 + Volume_2 * \gamma_2 + Volume_3 * \gamma_3$$

403 Considering the volume of the sphere, hemisphere, and cylinder, the above equation can be
404 written as:

405
$$\gamma_s = \frac{3}{4r} \left(\frac{2r}{3} - \frac{h}{2} \right) (\gamma_1 + \gamma_3) + \frac{3h\gamma_2}{4r}$$

406 Where h is thickness of ash layer and γ is dose rate due to gamma radiations.

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Table 1. List of samples along with geological location and history and age controls.

Serial no	Sample code	Latitude, Longitude	Expected age (ka)	Age comparison method	Reference and remarks
Volcanic ash fine grain sample					
1	PRL23-01	(15°19' N, 78° 8'E)	17 ± 1	pIRIR-SAR Feldspar	Anil, D., Personal communication, 2023
2	PRL23-02	(15°19' N, 78° 8'E)	21 ± 1	pIRIR-SAR Feldspar	Anil, D., Personal communication, 2023
3	PRL23-03	(15°08' N, 79°25'E)	32 ± 3	pIRIR-SAR Feldspar	MVP-T2-OSL 5 sample in Anil et al., (2025)
Pottery fine grain sample					
4	PRL23-04	(8°38' N, 78°03'E)	0.5 ± 0.1	IR50-SAR Feldspar	Sathiyaseelan, S., Personal communication, 2023
5	PRL23-05	(8°38' N, 78°03'E)	1.6 ± 0.4	IR50-SAR Feldspar	Sathiyaseelan, S., Personal communication, 2023
6	PRL23-06	(8°35' N , 77°54'E)	3.4 ± 0.3	pIRIR-SAR Feldspar	Morthekai, P., Personal communication, 2023
7	PRL23-07	(8°35' N , 77°54'E)	4.1 ± 0.4	pIRIR-SAR Feldspar	Morthekai, P., Personal communication, 2023
Fluvial coarse grain sample					
8	MHK-09-12	(22°13'N, 76°01'E)	65 ± 7	Quartz BSL-SAR	Mishra et al., 2013
9	MHK-09-13	(22°13'N, 76°01'E)	68 ± 7	Quartz BSL-SAR	Mishra et al., 2013
10	PRL23-08	(9°2'N, 78°16'E)	31 ± 2	Quartz BSL-SAR	Alappat, L., Personal communication, 2024
11	PRL23-09	(9°2'N, 78°16'E)	59 ± 3	Quartz BSL-SAR	Alappat, L., Personal communication, 2024
Fluvial fine grain sample					
10	PRL23-08	(9°2'N, 78°16'E)	31 ± 2	Quartz BSL-SAR	Alappat, L., Personal communication, 2024
11	PRL23-09	(9°2'N, 78°16'E)	59 ± 3	Quartz BSL-SAR	Alappat, L., Personal communication, 2024
12	PRL23-10	(29°6'N, 75°1'E)	1.0 ± 0.1	IR50-SAR Feldspar	Prasad, R.K., Personal communication, 2023
13	PRL23-11	(29°6'N, 75°1'E)	2.1 ± 0.1	IR50-SAR Feldspar	Prasad, R.K., Personal communication, 2023

Table 2. Estimated D_e values, fading value, recuperation, residual dose, and dose recovery ratio for all samples using pVIR-SAR protocol. Recuperation observed in all the samples is <5%.

The D_e values are corrected for fading, wherever applicable.

Sample name	pVIR D_e (Gy)	Dose rate (Gy/ka)	pVIR Age (ka)	pVIR g-value (% per decade)	pVIR Residual dose (Gy)	pVIR Dose recovery ratio
Volcanic ash fine grain sample						
PRL23-01	142 ± 4	8.5 ± 0.3	17 ± 1	1.1 ± 0.2	5.1 ± 0.4	1.00 ± 0.02
PRL23-02	181 ± 5	6.9 ± 0.2	26 ± 1	2.3 ± 0.2	4.9 ± 0.3	0.99 ± 0.02
PRL23-03	189 ± 13	7.4 ± 0.1 6.7 ± 0.4*	28 ± 3	1.1 ± 0.4	5.7 ± 0.2	1.01 ± 0.04
Pottery fine grain sample						
PRL23-04	6.3 ± 0.3	6.9 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.3	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-05	13.3 ± 0.3	7.4 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-06	13.1 ± 1.3	4.0 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.4	5.9 ± 0.6	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-07	14.2 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.2	4.0 ± 0.4	n.m.	n.m.
Fluvial coarse grain sample						
MHK-09-12	99 ± 5	1.5 ± 0.1	68 ± 6	0.5 ± 0.5	3.3 ± 0.2	1.01 ± 0.02
MHK-09-13	113 ± 7	1.7 ± 0.1	66 ± 6	0.2 ± 0.5	3.9 ± 0.1	1.05 ± 0.02
PRL23-08	236 ± 6	3.6 ± 0.2	66 ± 4	0.9 ± 0.4	10.0 ± 0.2	1.06 ± 0.03
PRL23-09	315 ± 16	2.7 ± 0.2	117 ± 10	1.5 ± 0.4	8.0 ± 0.1	1.03 ± 0.03
Fluvial fine grain sample						
PRL23-08	151 ± 2	3.9 ± 0.1	39 ± 1	1.0 ± 0.1	4.4 ± 0.1	1.06 ± 0.02
PRL23-09	219 ± 5	2.9 ± 0.1	76 ± 3	0.8 ± 0.5	8.1 ± 0.2	0.94 ± 0.02
PRL23-10	12 ± 1	5.8 ± 0.2	2.0 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.4	2.11 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.02
PRL23-11	17.2 ± 0.3	6.1 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.3	2.20 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.02

* Represents the dose rate after volumetric correction. n.m. denotes the not measured parameters.

Table 3. Estimated D_e values, fading value, recuperation, residual dose, and dose recovery ratio for all samples using IR- and pIRIR-SAR protocol. Recuperation observed in all the samples is <5%. The D_e values are corrected for fading, wherever applicable.

Sample name	IR / pIRIR D_e (Gy)	Dose rate (Gy/ka)	IR / pIRIR Age (ka)	IR / pIRIR g-value (% per decade)	IR / pIRIR Residual dose (Gy)	IR / pIRIR Dose recovery ratio
Volcanic ash fine grain sample						
PRL23-01	151 ± 9	9.0 ± 0.3	17 ± 1	1.5 ± 0.5	10.7 ± 0.8	0.94 ± 0.03
PRL23-02	156 ± 8	7.5 ± 0.3	21 ± 1	2.5 ± 0.4	10.3 ± 0.6	0.99 ± 0.03
PRL23-03	233 ± 22	8.0 ± 0.2 $7.2 \pm 0.3^*$	32 ± 3	1.9 ± 0.4	10.7 ± 1.2	0.93 ± 0.02
Pottery fine grains						
PRL23-04	4.0 ± 0.6	7.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 1.2	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-05	12 ± 3	7.5 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.4	7.1 ± 1.4	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-06	12.0 ± 0.6	3.5 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.4	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-07	15.8 ± 0.8	3.9 ± 0.3	4.1 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.3	n.m.	n.m.
Fluvial coarse grains						
MHK-09-12	112 ± 11	1.47 ± 0.12	76 ± 10	1.1 ± 0.6	15.6 ± 0.9	0.95 ± 0.02
MHK-09-13	126 ± 11	1.71 ± 0.12	73 ± 8	1.2 ± 0.7	5.5 ± 0.1	1.09 ± 0.03
PRL23-08	345 ± 23	3.6 ± 0.2	96 ± 8	1.4 ± 0.6	34.4 ± 0.5	1.11 ± 0.02
PRL23-09	422 ± 22	2.7 ± 0.2	156 ± 14	1.9 ± 0.6	32.0 ± 0.5	1.12 ± 0.03
Fluvial fine grains						
PRL23-08	293 ± 10	4.0 ± 0.1	73 ± 3	3.6 ± 0.2	22.8 ± 0.6	1.07 ± 0.03
PRL23-09	280 ± 6	3.1 ± 0.1	90 ± 3	0.8 ± 0.5	24.2 ± 1.4	0.96 ± 0.02
PRL23-10	5.5 ± 0.3	5.4 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.5	n.m.	n.m.
PRL23-11	12.2 ± 0.5	5.9 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.4	n.m.	n.m.

* Represents the dose rate after volumetric correction and font in italics represents the measurements for IRSL at 50 °C. n.m. stands for not measured.

Table 4. The details of the concentration of radioactive nuclides, alpha efficiency (a-values), water content, and sampling depth from the surface for all samples. The dose rates are calculated using the Dose Rate Calculator (DRc) software, assuming an infinite matrix (Tsokolas et al., 2016). The a-values are measured only for fine grain fractions.

Sample	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	K (%)	a-values			Water content (%)	Depth (cm)
				IR	pVIR	pIRIR		
Volcanic ash fine grain sample								
PRL23-01	5.7 ± 0.1	29.3 ± 0.6	3.7 ± 0.1	n.m.	0.067 ± 0.004	0.086 ± 0.007	15 ± 5	130
PRL23-02	4.3 ± 0.1	24.7 ± 0.8	2.9 ± 0.1	n.m.	0.088 ± 0.004	0.119 ± 0.006	15 ± 5	255
PRL23-03	5.0 ± 0.1	28.8 ± 0.6	3.3 ± 0.1	n.m.	0.060 ± 0.002	0.083 ± 0.004	20 ± 5	200
Pottery fine grains								
PRL23-04	4.2 ± 0.1	22.9 ± 0.5	3.6 ± 0.1	0.093 ± 0.001	0.071 ± 0.001	n.m.	20 ± 2	200
PRL23-05	2.9 ± 0.1	32.0 ± 1.1	3.2 ± 0.05	0.095 ± 0.002	0.087 ± 0.001	n.m.	20 ± 2	172
PRL23-06	2.5 ± 0.4	11.5 ± 1.8	1.8 ± 0.1	n.m.	0.099 ± 0.001	0.059 ± 0.001	8 ± 7	135
PRL23-07	2.5 ± 0.7	12.7 ± 2.6	1.9 ± 0.1	n.m.	0.110 ± 0.002	0.081 ± 0.001	10 ± 7	26
Fluvial coarse grains								
MHK-09-12	1.36 ± 0.27	3.62 ± 0.95	0.67 ± 0.09	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	15 ± 5	440
MHK-09-13	1.38 ± 1.33	4.44 ± 1.16	0.78 ± 0.06	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	15 ± 5	490
PRL23-08	0.77 ± 0.03	8.02 ± 0.19	2.3 ± 0.04	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	5.0 ± 2.5	90
PRL23-09	0.88 ± 0.03	7.88 ± 0.22	1.34 ± 0.03	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	5.0 ± 2.5	140
Fluvial fine grains								
PRL23-08	0.77 ± 0.03	8.02 ± 0.19	2.3 ± 0.04	n.m.	0.095 ± 0.002	0.105 ± 0.002	5.0 ± 2.5	90
PRL23-09	0.88 ± 0.03	7.88 ± 0.22	1.34 ± 0.03	n.m.	0.080 ± 0.006	0.108 ± 0.009	5.0 ± 2.5	140
PRL23-10	4.01 ± 0.05	16.81 ± 0.27	2.55 ± 0.04	0.034 ± 0.001	0.059 ± 0.001	n.m.	10 ± 5	50
PRL23-11	4.33 ± 0.05	17.34 ± 0.27	2.76 ± 0.04	0.047 ± 0.001	0.057 ± 0.001	n.m.	10 ± 5	200

n.m. stands for not measured.

Figure 1. Weight normalised shine down curves of pVIRSL from potassium feldspar (KF) (Devi et al., 2024), sodium feldspar (NaF), quartz (calibration quartz: batch 122) and empty disc measured after 20 Gy of beta dose, a preheat at 250 °C for 60 s, and violet stimulation at 50 °C for 100 s.

Figure 2. Fading rate measurements for sodium feldspar (NaF) sample for pVIRSL signal. Normalised pVIRSL luminescence intensity is plotted against measurement delay time to estimate fading rate. The weighted mean of athermal fading rates of fifteen aliquots is $0.1 \pm 0.2\%$ per decade.

Figure 3. Average fading rate values for all fine grain polymineral samples. Age corrections for fading rates less than one are not made (Buylaert et al., 2012). For young samples, the IRSL signal was used for controlled ages, except for those containing sanidine (PRL23-06 and PRL23-07), while for older samples, the pIRIRSL signal was measured. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 4. a) Alpha efficiencies of pVIRSL versus pIRIRSL, b) pVIRSL versus IRSL of all samples. Samples in the rectangle are different sets of pottery samples and shows a reverse trend of alpha efficiencies. Here the data only for fine grain samples are shown. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 5. Relation between alpha efficiency and fading rates of a) pVIRSL, b) IRSL and c) pIRIRSL for all samples. The data points in the rectangle are pottery samples and have higher fading rates possibly because of the presence of sanidine. Here the data only for fine grain samples are shown. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 6. Polymineral fine grain pVIR ages plotted against the IR and pIRIR ages. Here error reported are standard errors. Ages were corrected for fading wherever applicable. For young samples, the IRSL signal was used for controlled ages, except for those containing sanidine, while for older samples, the pIRIRSL signal was measured. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean. The blue lines indicate 20% offset in the data.

Figure 7. Comparison of coarse and fine grain pVIR and pIRIR ages with the expected quartz ages of fluvial samples. Ages were corrected for fading wherever applicable. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean. CG and FG stands for coarse and fine grain fractions. The blue lines indicate 20% offset in the data.

Volcanic Ash samples

Figure S1. Typical decay curves (a, d, and g), dose response curves (b, c, and h) and fading rate measurements: variation of normalised intensity with delay time (c, f, and i) of pVIRSL of volcanic ash fine grain samples PRL23-01, PRL23-02, and PRL23-03. Each graph is from a single aliquot.

Figure S2. The typical pVIRSL decay curves (a, d, g and j), dose response curves (b, e, h and k) and fading rate measurements: variation of normalised intensity with delay time (c, f, i, and l) for pottery fine grain samples PRL23-04, PRL23-05, PRL23-06, and PRL23-07. Each graph is from a single aliquot.

Figure S3. The pVIRSL decay curves (a and d), dose response curves (b and e) and fading rate measurements: variation of normalised intensity with delay time (c and f) for pVIRSL for fine grain fluvial samples PRL23-10 and PRL23-11. Data in each graph is representing a single aliquot.

Figure S4. Normalised pVIRSL intensity as a function of delay time for fading rate measurements of fine grains from (a) PRL23-08 and (b) PRL23-09.

Figure S5. a) OSL sampling of PRL23-03 volcanic ash site. b) Zoomed view of volcanic ash layer deposit. The thickness of ash layer is ~30 cm. A sphere of radius 30 cm is considered for volumetric corrections for dose deposited by gamma radiations (Appendix I).

Table S1. Parameters for pVIR-SAR protocol (Devi et al., 2024).

Step	Treatment	Observed measurement
1.	Natural signal	
2.	Preheat (250 °C, 60 s)	Removes thermally unstable signal
3.	VSL (50 °C, 100 s)	
4.	IRSL (200 °C, 100 s)	L_n, L_x
5.	Test Dose (50-80% D_e)	
6.	Preheat (250 °C, 60 s)	Removes thermally unstable signal
7.	VSL (50 °C, 100 s)	
8.	IRSL (200 °C, 100 s)	T_n, T_x
9.	VSL (350 °C, 200 s)	Illumination
10.	IRSL (350 °C, 200 s)	Illumination
11.	Give dose and return to step 2	

Table S2. Parameters for IR-SAR protocol ($T = 50$ °C) (Wallinga et al., 2000).

Step	Treatment	Observed measurement
1	Natural signal	
2	Preheat, 60 s at 250 °C	Removes thermally unstable signal
3	IR stimulation, 100 s at 50 °C	L_n, L_x
4	Test dose	
5	Preheat, 60 s at 320 °C	Removes thermally unstable signal
6	IR stimulation, 100 s at 50 °C	T_n, T_x
7	IR stimulation, 200 s at 100 °C	Illumination
8	Give dose and return to step 2	

Table S3. Parameters for pIRIR-SAR ($T = 290$ °C) protocol (Buylaert et al., 2009).

Step	Treatment	Observed measurement
1	Natural signal	
2	Preheat, 60 s at 320 °C	Removes thermally unstable signal
3	IR stimulation, 100 s at 50 °C	
4	IR stimulation, 100 s at 290 °C	L_n, L_x
5	Test dose	
6	Preheat, 60 s at 320 °C	Removes thermally unstable signal
7	IR stimulation, 100 s at 50 °C	
8	IR stimulation, 100 s at 290 °C	T_n, T_x
9	IR stimulation, 200 s at 325 °C	Illumination
10	Give dose and return to step 2	

Table S4. Estimated D_e values and ages for all samples using pVIR-, IR- and pIRIR-SAR protocol considering residual dose subtraction. Fonts in italics represents the measurements for IRSL at 50 °C.

Sample name	pVIR D_e (Gy)	IR / pIRIR D_e (Gy)	pVIR Age (ka)	IR / pIRIR Age (ka)
Volcanic ash fine grains				
PRL23-01	137 ± 4	140 ± 9	17 ± 1	16 ± 1
PRL23-02	176 ± 5	146 ± 8	26 ± 1	20 ± 1
PRL23-03	183 ± 13	222 ± 22	27 ± 3	31 ± 3
Pottery fine grains				
PRL23-04	6.3 ± 0.3	<i>4.0 ± 0.6</i>	0.9 ± 0.1	<i>0.5 ± 0.1</i>
PRL23-05	13.3 ± 0.3	<i>12 ± 3</i>	1.8 ± 0.1	<i>1.6 ± 0.4</i>
PRL23-06	13.1 ± 1.3	12.0 ± 0.6	3.3 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.3
PRL23-07	14.2 ± 0.1	15.8 ± 0.8	3.3 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.4
Fluvial coarse grains				
MHK-09-12	96 ± 5	96 ± 11	58 ± 7	58 ± 9
MHK-09-13	109 ± 7	120 ± 11	60 ± 7	66 ± 9
PRL23-08	226 ± 6	311 ± 23	63 ± 3	86 ± 8
PRL23-09	307 ± 16	390 ± 22	114 ± 9	144 ± 12
Fluvial fine grains				
PRL23-08	147 ± 2	270 ± 10	38 ± 1	68 ± 3
PRL23-09	211 ± 5	327 ± 7	73 ± 3	107 ± 4
PRL23-10	9.6 ± 0.5	<i>5.5 ± 0.3</i>	1.6 ± 0.1	<i>1.0 ± 0.1</i>
PRL23-11	15.0 ± 0.3	<i>12.2 ± 0.5</i>	2.5 ± 0.1	<i>2.1 ± 0.1</i>

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